

Theoretical study on the reaction mechanism of proton transfer in cysteinamine

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Abstract : We present detailed theoretical studies of the proton transfer in the isolated cysteinamine and H₂O-assisted system, employing B3LYP, Hartree-Fock (HF) and MP2 methods at the large basis set. The barrier heights for amino hydrogen atom transfer are lower than carboic hydrogen atom transfer in all configurations, implying the much easier transfer of the amino hydrogen atom. When the H₂O is assisted in the process, it can facilitate the proton transfer.

Keywords : Proton transfer, cysteinamine, H₂O-assisted system.

Proton transfer reactions are important in many chemical and biological systems¹⁻⁷. A particular type of proton transfer is one in which catalyst molecules can mediate the process by serving as a bridge between the donor and the acceptor sites. Many amino acids could exist in alternative chemical forms, differing in that only a proton shifts in the molecule. The tautomeric shifts are chemically involved in the bond-making and breaking steps in catalysis of enzymes, which may lead to base-pair changes or even mutations. So it is quite necessary for us to understand the mechanism of proton transfer process as deeply as possible. In this study, we use cysteinamine as an example to examine the tautomerization of its keto form to its enol form.

Cysteine (HSCH₂CHNH₂COOH) is one of the roughly 21 amino acids common in nature, which is usually chosen as a good model for studying biological systems exhibiting the amino acid type of bonding and DNA structures. It can resist radiation and cure irradiation sickness, so it has been researched by more and more people⁸⁻¹¹. Compared with cysteine, cysteinamine (HSCH₂CHNH₂CONH₂) uses the amino group to take the place of its hydroxyl group, so it must have more biological activity. However, to our best knowledge, the systematical studies on proton transfer process of cysteinamine have not been performed, so it is a vacuous field for us to fill.

In this paper there are two types of hydrogen atoms in cysteinamine that can transfer : the carboic hydrogen atom and the amino hydrogen atom, and the tautomeric

products are HSCH₂CNH₂COHNH₂ and HSCH₂CHNH₂COHNH, respectively. The present study has been to adhere to the following question : (1) Which hydrogen atom is more favorable to transfer, the amino hydrogen atom or the carboic hydrogen atom? (2) If a water molecule is added to this system, will it facilitate or protect the transfer process? (3) To find the most favorable geometry of proton transfer.

Computations :

Density functional theory (DFT) is a very useful tool in studying the chemistry of molecules. It can give reliable geometries and properties comparable in accuracy to experimental values. Therefore, the geometries of the reactants, transition states and products for the tautomerization are optimized using B3LYP method and the Hartree-Fock (HF) method applying 6-311 + +G(d,p) basis set. For comparison, the MP2 calculations are also performed at the chosen basis set. Vibrational frequencies have been obtained at the same level for characterization of stationary points and zero-point energy (ZPE) corrections. The validity of the transition state structures is further validated by the IRC. All calculations are performed with the Gaussian 98 program¹².

Results and discussion

An electro spray ionization ion trap mass spectrometer had been used to determine the proton affinities of glycine, proline, cysteine and phenylalanine by Pepe¹³. In our works, the *ab initio* calculation also has been car-

ried out. We calculated five stable configurations of the cysteinamine, including a pairs of mirror-image configurations (C2 and C3). All of these configurations can have two types of hydrogen atoms which can transfer to O atom of the carbonyl group : the amino hydrogen atom and the carboic hydrogen atom. Since the mirror-image configurations are identical to each other in energy and in structural parameters except for the dihedral angles, we just take one configuration (C2) of two mirror-image configurations for instance to illustrate the phenomenon of proton transfer. The structures of five configurations of cysteinamine are shown in Fig. 1 and the most interesting geometrical parameters are calculated at the HF, B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) and MP2/6-31G, which are listed in Table 1. Notice that, the amino group and the carbonyl group are nearly in a plane in all of the five configurations; but it is different in the HC* and the C*CO plane. We can see that the HC* is against to the C*CO plane in C1 and C2, they are nearly in a plane in C4 but have an angle in C5.

The transfer process of carboic hydrogen atom :

The hydrogen atom can transfer from the HC* group to the carbonyl group, the selected geometrical parameters which we calculated are listed in Table 2. The proton transfer process is illustrated in Fig. 2.

We take C1 for instance to illustrate the proton transfer. For the normal mechanism (R-TS-P), the transition state appears to hold a co-planar four-membered-ring. From the examination of the structural changes from reactant to product at B3LYP, HF at the 6-311++G(d,p) level, for simplicity, the results with MP2/6-31G are not listed, it can be seen that the HC*C bond angle undergoes compression first, and then C*H bond starts to lengthen. The cysteinamine must undergo larger struc-

Fig. 1. Optimized structures of cysteinamine in the gaseous phase calculated at the B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p).

tural changes that are energetically expensive. The HC*C bond angle is compressed from a value of 105.48° to 64.271° at B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) level, a 39% decrease. The C*H bond is then stretched from 1.096 to 1.591 Å, an increase of 45% to reach the transition state. Also we can see from Table 2, in the reaction process, the CO bond length gradually increases while C*C bond length decreases. In a word, the structural changes re-

Table 1. The selected geometrical parameters of the cysteinamine configurations (reactants)*

	C1	C2	C4	C5
R_{OC}	1.222 ^a (1.197 ^b) 1.270 ^c	1.222 ^a (1.199 ^b) 1.270 ^c	1.2221 ^a (1.196 ^b) 1.268 ^c	1.219 ^a (1.196 ^b) 1.269 ^c
$R_{N^*H^*}$	1.008 ^a (0.993 ^b) 1.012 ^c	1.0078 ^a (0.993 ^b) 1.011 ^c	1.009 ^a (0.995 ^b) 1.012 ^c	1.008 ^a (0.994 ^b) 1.010 ^c
R_{CN}	1.355 ^a (1.348 ^b) 1.368 ^c	1.353 ^a (1.343 ^b) 1.366 ^c	1.363 ^a (1.357 ^b) 1.379 ^c	1.361 ^a (1.351 ^b) 1.368 ^c
R_{CC^*}	1.545 ^a (1.534 ^b) 1.546 ^c	1.546 ^a (1.533 ^b) 1.546 ^c	1.546 ^a (1.536 ^b) 1.543 ^c	1.551 ^a (1.538 ^b) 1.547 ^c
R_{C^*H}	1.096 ^a (1.086 ^b) 1.101 ^c	1.098 ^a (1.089 ^b) 1.104 ^c	1.093 ^a (1.082 ^b) 1.099 ^c	1.095 ^a (1.085 ^b) 1.101 ^c
\angle_{OCN^*}	123.378 ^a (122.979 ^b) 123.382 ^c	124.093 ^a (123.416 ^b) 124.124 ^c	122.644 ^a (122.216 ^b) 122.415 ^c	122.720 ^a (122.267 ^b) 124.087 ^c
\angle_{CC^*H}	105.48 ^a (105.496 ^b) 107.109 ^c	104.335 ^a (103.846 ^b) 106.168 ^c	103.533 ^a (103.466 ^b) 103.595 ^c	104.64 ^a (104.594 ^b) 106.630 ^c
$\angle_{H^*N^*C}$	118.940 ^a (118.081 ^b) 119.345 ^c	119.240 ^a (118.661 ^b) 119.552 ^c	119.693 ^a (117.601 ^b) 118.217 ^c	118.447 ^a (118.024 ^b) 119.431 ^c
\angle_{OCNH^*}	-0.916 ^a (-4.490 ^b) 0.840 ^c	-0.612 ^a (0.282 ^b) -0.591 ^c	3.150 ^a (8.339 ^b) 1.441 ^c	-1.870 ^a (-2.075 ^b) -0.815 ^c
\angle_{HC^*CO}	-92.490 ^a (-102.415 ^b) -93.610 ^c	-83.057 ^a (84.203 ^b) -87.883 ^c	-12.773 ^a (4.807 ^b) -13.741 ^c	59.100 ^a (59.535 ^b) 82.894 ^c

*Distances in Å, angles in degree, ^a, ^b and ^c represent B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p), HF/6-311++G(d,p) and MP2/6-31G, respectively.

Table 2. The selected geometrical parameters of the transition (TS) and products (P) of the proton transfer process of carbolic hydrogen atom in the gaseous phase calculated at B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p)^a

	R _{OH}	R _{C*H}	R _{CC*}	R _{OC}	A _{C*HO}	A _{CC*H}	A _{C*CO}	A _{HOC}
C1 TS	1.232 (1.186)	1.591 (1.550)	1.459 (1.479)	1.291 (1.260)	104.506 (106.424)	64.271 (63.745)	109.196 (106.736)	
P	0.966 (0.943)		1.347 (1.327)	1.370 (1.351)			121.108 (121.428)	107.845 (109.032)
C2 TS	1.246 (1.193)	1.560 (1.533)	1.461 (1.476)	1.191 (1.261)	105.515 (107.031)	64.458 (63.783)	108.948 (106.776)	
P	0.966 (0.943)		1.347 (1.327)	1.370 (1.351)			121.054 (121.3447)	108.140 (109.198)
C4 TS	1.196 (1.180)	1.598 (1.541)	1.486 (1.486)	1.285 (1.261)	106.235 (107.315)	64.478 (63.685)	108.235 (107.315)	
P	0.976 (0.948)		1.357 (1.336)	1.352 (1.334)			121.513 (122.530)	104.315 (107.337)
C5 TS	1.247 (1.192)	1.557 (1.533)	1.457 (1.475)	1.292 (1.261)	105.433 (106.835)	64.325 (63.548)	108.900 (106.607)	
P	0.975 (0.944)		1.354 (1.333)	1.363 (1.345)			123.384 (123.845)	108.859 (111.003)

^aDistances in Å, angles in degree, data in the brackets are obtained with MP2/6-31G.

Fig. 2. Optimized structures of the transition states and the products of the transfer process of carbolic hydrogen atom in the gaseous phase calculated at the B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p).

fect the process of the formation of a new bond (O–H) and the rupture of an old bond (C*–H). This means H atom transfer from C* atom to O atom, it will have one and only one imaginary frequency in the transition state.

For H₂O-assisted tautomerization (R(H₂O)-TS(H₂O)-P(H₂O)), the stable geometry of reactant R(H₂O) is the cyclic double-hydrogen bonded structure in Fig. 4. The water molecule acts simultaneously as a proton donor and acceptor. Two hydrogen bond distances are 3.375 Å and 2.040 Å, respectively. This is a nearly co-planar six membered ring structure with an O–H bond of H₂O stretching out the plane. The role of the water is to serve as a proton relay. The breaking of the C*H bond is accompanied by the H atom from C* to O_w and another H from the water to O, forming P(H₂O). For P(H₂O), we can see only one hydrogen bonded system while the hydrogen bond is 1.789 Å. In comparison with the normal tautomerization, the obvious difference is that the O_wHC* angle has to be compressed by 8.5°. At the same time, the C*–H bond increases by 37% (from 1.095 to 1.505 Å). We may predict the large reduction in the classical energy barrier from the normal to the water-catalyzed case attributed to the water acting as a catalyst through the stabilization of the transition state.

The activation energies of the transfer processes of the carbolic hydrogen atom for four configurations are presented in Table 4. The values in parenthesis are including zero point vibrational energy (ZPE) corrections. From the Table, we can see that the relative order of the activation energy is C5 < C4 < C1 < C2. The results indicate that configuration C5 is the most favorable structure for the carbolic hydrogen atom to transfer, and its activation energy is just 266.3 kJ/mol at the B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) calculation. However, C2 is the most difficult. At the same time, the involvement of a water mol-

Fig. 3. Optimized structures of the transition states and the products of the transfer process of amino hydrogen atom in the gas phase calculated at the B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p).

ecule lowers the activation energy by 91.5 kJ/mol, which is a good proof that water molecule has a superior catalytic effect.

The transfer process of amino hydrogen atom :

The hydrogen atom can also transfer from the amino group to the carbonyl group. And the selected geometrical parameters which we calculated are listed in Table 3.

Fig. 4. Optimized structures with water molecule of the reactant, the transition states and the products of all the transfer process calculated at the B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p).

The proton transfer process is illustrated in Fig. 3.

In comparison with the carbolic hydrogen atom transfer, we also take C1 for instance to illustrate the proton transfer. From the reactant geometry, we noticed that the amino group and the carbonyl group are nearly in a plane, which may predict that it is easier for the amino hydrogen atom to transfer to O than the carbolic hydrogen atom.

We used the B3LYP, HF at the 6-311++G(d,p) level and calculated the transition states and products in Table 3, for simplicity, the results with MP2/6-31G are not listed. From the geometric parameters of the transition state, we notice that the H*N*C bond angle is compressed from 118.940° to 73.815°, a 38% decrease; and the N*H* bond is then stretched from 1.008 to 1.338 Å, an increase of 32.7%. Two changed values are less than those

Table 3. The selected geometrical parameters of the transition (TS) and products (P) of the proton transfer process of amino hydrogen atom in gaseous phase calculated at B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p)^a

	R _{OH*}	R _{N*H*}	R _{CN*}	R _{OC}	A _{OH*N}	A _{H*N*C}	A _{OCN*}	A _{H*OC}
C1 TS	1.315 (1.285)	1.338 (1.307)	1.302 (1.286)	1.297 (1.272)	104.167 (104.167)	73.815 (73.644)	107.277 (106.751)	
P	0.969 (0.945)		1.263 (1.245)	1.360 (1.339)			119.892 (120.107)	106.319 (107.926)
C2 TS	1.319 (1.288)	1.337 (1.307)	1.301 (1.285)	1.296 (1.272)	104.226 (104.779)	73.679 (73.562)	107.646 (107.014)	
P	0.968 (0.945)		1.262 (1.244)	1.361 (1.340)			120.544 (120.540)	106.483 (108.054)
C4 TS	1.317 (1.284)	1.337 (1.304)	1.307 (1.293)	1.294 (1.266)	104.110 (104.755)	73.568 (73.426)	107.179 (106.461)	
P	0.969 (0.945)		1.266 (1.247)	1.362 (1.339)			119.364 (119.451)	106.635 (108.321)
C5 TS	1.364 (1.320)	1.390 (1.337)	1.320 (1.303)	1.340 (1.270)	104.182 (104.767)	73.725 (73.482)	107.642 (107.003)	
P	0.969 (0.945)		1.266 (1.248)	1.356 (1.335)			119.908 (120.126)	107.010 (108.514)

^aDistances in Å, angles in degree, data in the brackets are obtained with MP2/6-31G.

Table 4. The activation energies of all the transfer processes (kJ/mol)

Activation energy	C1	C2	C4	C5
Carbonic H transfer	278.4 (341.7)	280.7 (354.1)	270.3 (325.6)	266.3 (321.3)
Amino H transfer	204.9 (259.5)	207.2 (260.6)	198.1 (250.5)	181.6 (236.4)
Carbonic H(H ₂ O) transfer	186.9 (200.1)			
Amino H(H ₂ O) transfer	97.7 (111.8)			

Data in the brackets are obtained with MP2/6-31G.

in the carbolic hydrogen atom transfer, which is another factor contributing to the lower energy barrier of the transition state. At the same time, the CO bond length gradually increases while CN* bond length decreases. There is one and only one imaginary frequency in the transition state, which indicates a new bond (O-H*) and the rupture of an old bond (N*-H*).

Similar to the H₂O-monomer assisted process in the carbolic hydrogen atom transfer, it also has the cyclic double-hydrogen bonded structure in the reactant R(H₂O). The values of the two hydrogen bonds are 1.890 Å and 2.075 Å, respectively. The obvious difference with the H₂O-assisted carbolic hydrogen atom transfer is the O_wH*N*, which does not decrease but increases 10.4° (from 137.785° to 148.246°). At the same time, the N*-H* bond increases 26% (from 1.016 to 1.286 Å). We can see the water acting as a catalyst through the stabilization of the transition state and reducing the activation energy barrier.

From Table 4 of the activation energies of the amino hydrogen atom transfer for four configurations, we find that the relative order of the activation energy is C5 < C4 < C1 < C2, but all of the values are less than those in the carbolic hydrogen atom transfer, respectively. So we concluded that the amino hydrogen atom transfer is

easier than the carbolic hydrogen atom transfer. Same as the carbolic hydrogen atom transfer, C5 is the easiest and C2 is the most difficult in amino hydrogen atom transfer. And the involvement of a water molecule lowers the activation energy by 107.2 kJ/mol, which indicates the water also acting as a catalyst through the stabilization of the transition state.

In conclusion, Computational investigations of the proton transfer in the isolated cysteinamine and H₂O-assisted system have been performed employing B3LYP, Hartree-Fock (HF) methods at the large basis set 6-311++G(d,p) and the second-order moller-pleeset perturbation (MP2) method. All of the significant transition states which describe the proton transfer process have been systemically studied. Through the calculations, it is much easier for the amino hydrogen atom to transfer than the carbolic hydrogen atom in all of the five configurations. The involvement of a water molecule can not only stabilize the transition states, but also greatly reduce the activation energy. Therefore, the proton transfer will be easily facilitated by the presence of one water molecule.

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